

***STUDYING THE MOTIVATION OF YOUNG ATHLETE GIRLS TO ENGAGE
IN ARTISTIC GYMNASTICS.***

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IN ARTISTIC GYMNASTICS.***

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Annotation

The article presents information on the results of young gymnasts belonging to the control and experimental groups in the initial and final parts of the pedagogical experience, their statistical characteristics, growth during the experience, and competition motives.

Keywords: Young gymnasts, sports motive, competition motive, average value, training process, initial training group.

Аннотация

В статье представлены данные о результатах, полученных в начале и конце педагогического эксперимента, их статистических характеристиках, росте в ходе эксперимента, мотивациях соревнований юных гимнасток в контрольной и экспериментальной группах.

Ключевые слова: Молодые гимнастки, спортивный мотив, соревновательный мотив, среднее значение, тренировочный процесс, начальная учебная группа.

The relevance of the topic. Currently, attention is being paid to all types of sports, creating favorable conditions for athletes, therefore, the important task of growing sports reserves is one of the major tasks facing sports coaches. This not

only allows you to achieve success in competitions at various levels of sports, but also serves to develop the sports movement in our country, increases patriotism, and creates conditions for self-awareness. Personal development through sports begins in childhood, where motivation is the driving force behind participation in sports. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 5, 2018 No. UP-5368 "On measures to radically improve the system of state administration in the field of physical culture and sports," Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 23, 2022 No. RP-449, "On measures to further develop gymnastics sports", In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 9, 2011 No. 253 "On the organization of the activities of the Republican Specialized Children's and Youth Sports School of Olympic Reserve for Artistic Gymnastics," the further development of this sport is considered relevant.

Purpose of the research: development of a program for developing the sports motivation of young female athletes in rhythmic gymnastics through games and its testing during sports training.

Research methods: Analysis of literature, pedagogical observation, video analysis, pedagogical experience, mathematical and statistical methods.

Research results and discussion: At the beginning and end of the pedagogical experiment, we summarized and analyzed the materials of existing scientific and methodological literature and periodicals of young athletes in control and experimental groups engaged in rhythmic gymnastics (15 athletes each), whose levels of preparedness were as close as possible to each other, and based on our personal experience, we recorded the results of the following methodology characterizing the motives of sports activities.

Table-1

Comparison of statistical characteristics of the results recorded during the experiment and their changes during the experiment on the differences in the significance of the motives for sports activity in the training stage of artistic gymnasts in the control (n=15) and experimental (n=15) groups

Motives	Average value			Meaning H-test	Level of importance
	Initial training groups				
	1 years	2 years	3 years		
External	2.409091	2.075949	0,900000	23.05288	0,0000
Perception	2.704545	2.063291	1.000000	20.05259	0,0002
Game	2.806818	2.772152	1.733333	27.50786	0,0000
Position	2.568182	2.088608	1.566667	8.568540	0,0356
Social	3.000000	2.227848	1,100000	22.27134	0,0001
Approvals	2.443182	2.379747	2.300000	12.74066	0,0052

Note: Average value (in percentages) in the study of the motives of young gymnasts in preliminary training groups

The analysis of the data presented in this table showed that the results of the tests of the sports motives of the test-aged female gymnasts of the control and experimental groups during the experiment were significantly different from each other compared to the corresponding differences at the beginning of the experiment. For example, in 1-2-3 years of initial training in the initial training groups, the level of importance for external perception and play was 0.0000, and for positional motifs, it represented an indicator of 0.0356, and all other types of motifs determined by indicators close to each other for training groups.

Thus, in the initial study group of the 1st stage, we can say that all studied motives are almost equal. This may indicate disparity and inconsistency in the need-motivation field of children in this group. At the same time, it can be noted that social and game motives, as well as the motive of knowledge, are more prominent. In the initial study group of 2 years of study, the motive of the game is the leading motive against the background of other motives. In the initial preparation group of the 3-year study, the game motive remains one of the leaders, but its importance is lower than in previous years (previous stages of preparation). At this stage of preparation, the most important thing is the motivation of gymnasts to be approved by their coaches, parents and peers. It should be noted that during the transition of children to the third year of school, the values of all motives (except for the approval motive) decrease sharply. At this stage, the decrease in the importance of the game motive is especially noteworthy. It should also be noted that external motivation, cognitive motivation and social motivation are the least important in 3-year-old primary school children.

Table-2.***Differences in the importance of sports competition motives between the control and experimental groups of gymnasts in the initial training group (t-test)***

Motives for doing sports	Average value		t - sinov qiymati	Muhimlik darajasi
	Control group	Experimental group		
1- annual training				
Communication	3.17795	3.19182	0.126342	0,899756
Material products	3.41386	2.73295	2.788480	0,006518
Physical perfection	4.27273	4.33409	0,929761	0.355097
Improved well-being and health	2.93955	2.95273	-0,073736	0,941392
Acquiring skills and knowledge useful for life	3.62318	3.63705	1.269854	0.207562
Increasing reputation, striving for glory	3.70000	3.71027	0.888664	0,376663
2- annual training				
Communication	2,63000	3.18833	-1,25592	0.237696
Perception	3.29167	3.95833	-1,14873	0.277401
Material products	2.83500	3.39333	-0,97275	0.353621
Development of virtues	3.54500	4.39667	-1,99848	0,073574
Improved well-being and health	2,71000	3.16333	-0,86246	0.408641
Acquiring skills and knowledge useful for life	3.02833	3.63167	-1,41006	0.188858
Increasing prestige, striving for glory	3.13333	4.15000	-1,97020	0,077118
Collectivistic direction	3.40833	4.18000	-1.35303	0.205841
3- annual training				
Communication	3.70000	3.00250	1.469143	0.185248
Perception	4,40000	3.50000	2.066685	0.077596
Material products	3.52800	2.81500	1.276758	0.242408
Development of virtues	4.50400	4.19000	0,902759	0,396654
Physical perfection	4,56000	4.57500	0,051897	0,960060
The need for excitement	4.04600	4,05000	0,027763	0,978626
Acquiring skills and knowledge useful for life	2.99750	3,90000	1.759101	0,121962
Increasing reputation, striving for glory	4.02000	4.38750	0,946744	0,375296

Explanation: Studying the competition motives of young athletes rhythmic gymnasts in preliminary training groups.

Differences in motives for doing sports in all training groups, the highest result was the motive of physical excellence, which increased from 4.27273 to 4.57500, increasing reputation, striving for fame, the result increased between 3.02833 and 4.38750, it can be seen that it has changed from 3.17795 to 3.70000 according to the communication motive. Material products recorded low results from 3.41386 to 2.81500, It is reflected that the need for excitement has developed between 4.04600 and 4.05000, in addition, the development of qualities between 3.54500 and 4.50400 was determined during the experiment.

In conclusion: The fact that the differences in the importance of sports competition motives between the control and experimental groups of the gymnasts in the studied preliminary training group were shown with clear differences both at the beginning of the experiment and at the end of the experiment, their main competition motives are fame 28.8%, material needs 18.9%, the motive for physical qualities is 14.7%, and the remaining material needs are also reflected in clear numbers. In the research conducted to determine the sports and competition motivation of young gymnasts, average growth prevailed in the 1-year preliminary preparation groups, It can be seen that there is a significant difference in the level of high and medium growth in the 2-year training groups.

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